

IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS THROUGH THEIR INTEREST IN AMERICAN, AUSTRALIAN, CANADIAN CULTURE

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Annotation: *This article reveals the improvement of professional competence of future English language teachers through their interest in American, Australian, Canadian culture.*

Key words: *development, competence, technologies, experience, future teacher, education, professional activity.*

INTRODUCTION

The major changes taking place in the socio-economic life of the modern society lead to a qualitative change in the content and nature of professional activity, the qualities that determine the level of socio-professional mobilization and competitiveness of future teachers (theoretical knowledge and practical training unity and unity, professional competence, flexibility and professional mobilization, mastering methods of solving professional tasks, ability to solve various professional problems, self-confidence, responsibility, striving for success, active life and professional position, regular use of practical experience preparation for enrichment) is required.

The main goal of modern education is to prepare a person who is fully developed for society and the state, socially adaptable to society and work, and who can work on himself. As the President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoev, said about this, "the solution of the most urgent problems of society depends on the professional knowledge, professional competence, high skills, rich spiritual and moral image, and cultural level of the high-level specialists. is an action"[2].

Also, Presidential Decree No. 4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" is the most important program document that defines the priorities of state policy in the medium term. Based on this document, a number of reforms in the field of education are being implemented.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Canadian, American, Australian cultures are interrelated. Many teachers ignore the culture and try to teach English and content knowledge without knowing the background of their students. Teachers should be open to

learning about new cultures and their students should embrace all cultures in the classroom. By trying to learn about each other's values and beliefs, teacher and student not only increase the effectiveness of ESL, but also make it a successful learning experience for all involved. A student who is shy or reluctant to answer questions may be more open when talking about their values that they associate with home life.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that not only the orientation of the education to the learner, but also the teacher's psychological readiness for pedagogical activity is important in providing education and training to a person. In such cases, it is necessary to pay special attention to the level of professional competence of the teacher. Acceptance of the competent approach in the educational system as the conceptual basis of educational reforms, the introduction of the competent approach to the educational system is based on the educational goal, content, form of teaching, teaching methods, pedagogical and information technologies, control methods and requires making serious changes in the role of teacher and learner.

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